

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R9.3 Project launch event

Authors: Patrik Fiferna, Vít Hladík, Eva Hudečková,
Vladimír Kolejka, Eva Šedinová (CGS)

March 2021

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1 INTRODUCTION

On 5 March 2021, the Czech Geological Survey organized the conference Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS, focused on the CO₂ capture and storage technology. Due to the regulations taken by the government to overcome the coronavirus epidemic, the conference took place online

The conference was also the launch event of the CO₂-SPICER a METAMORPH projects. These projects focus on research and development of CO₂ capture and storage technologies and are funded by the Norway Grants and the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic within the KAPPA programme.

The guests were welcomed by the ambassador of the Kingdom of Norway in the Czech Republic, H. E. Robert Kvile, the Director of the Czech Geological Survey, Mr. Zdeněk Venera, and the Director of the InoCure company, Mr. Matej Buzgo.

The first session ‘Setting the scene’ contained four keynote talks by representatives of the Czech Ministries of Environment and Industry & Trade, the Norwegian Research Council and the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic. The second session ‘CCS projects of the KAPPA programme’ was devoted to presentations of the two KAPPA programme CCS projects – CO-SPICER and METAMORPH. The third session ‘Other CCUS initiatives in Czechia’ provided an overview of four additional CCS-related projects currently running in the Czech Republic and funded from other programmes. A final discussion concluded the 4-hour conference programme.

A total of 89 participants from 37 institutions from the Czech Republic and Norway registered for the conference, and the maximum online participation at one moment was 70 people.

An online registration form was created in preparation for the conference. The public was informed about the preparation of the conference through three announcements. Conference language was English and the used SW platform was Webex. After the conference, news were published on the websites <http://co2-spicer.geology.cz>, www.geology.cz and <http://www.geology.cz/ccs>. Conference presentations were also made available on the project website at <https://co2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads>.

2 EVENT DOCUMENTATION

2.1 Online registration form

Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS

Launch event of CCS-related research and innovation projects supported from the TAČR KAPPA programme

Launch event registration - 5 March 2021

Leaders of the newly launched Czech-Norwegian research & innovation projects CO2-SPICER and METAMORPH, supported from the CCS part of the TAČR KAPPA programme, would like to invite you to an online Launch event. The half-day web-conference will not only introduce the two projects in question, but also provide insight to a broader context of the CCS technology development in the framework of the accelerated economy decarbonisation efforts in the Czech Republic and Europe. The presentations will also include other CCUS projects and initiatives currently ongoing in Czechia, reflecting the increased momentum of the CCUS technology development we are now experiencing.

Save the date in your calendars; more information and further instructions will follow soon. CO2-SPICER and METAMORPH are looking forward to meeting you at this interesting event.

Name and surname *

Text stručné odpovědi

Name of the organization *

Text stručné odpovědi

Email *

Text stručné odpovědi

Phone

Text stručné odpovědi

Additional information

Text dlouhé odpovědi

2.2 Announcements

2.2.1 1st Announcement

SAVE THE DATE!

Online, 5 March 2021, 9:00-13:00

Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS

Launch event of CCS-related research and innovation projects supported from the TAČR KAPPA programme

Leaders of the newly launched Czech-Norwegian research & innovation projects CO₂-SPICER and METAMORPH, supported from the CCS part of the TAČR KAPPA programme, would like to invite you to an online Launch event. The half-day web-conference will not only introduce the two projects in question, but also provide insight to a broader context of the CCS technology development in the framework of the accelerated economy decarbonisation efforts in the Czech Republic and Europe. The presentations will also include other CCUS projects and initiatives currently ongoing in Czechia, reflecting the increased momentum of the CCUS technology development we are now experiencing.

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Programme **Kappa**

**T A
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Tentative agenda

8:30 – 9:00 Virtual welcome coffee, chat and connection testing

9:00 – 9:30 Welcome and introduction

- Welcome, introduction and housekeeping rules – Vit Hladik (Czech Geological Survey)
- Group photo
- Welcoming addresses:
 - H. E. Robert Kvile, Ambassador of the Kingdom of Norway to the Czech Republic
 - Zdeněk Venera, Director of Czech Geological Survey – tbc
 - Matej Buzgo, CEO, InoCure

9:30 – 10:55 Session 1 – Setting the scene

- Decarbonisation of Czech economy – Pavel Zámyslický, Director of the Energy and Climate Protection Dept. of the Ministry of Environment of the Czech Republic
- Presentation by the Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic – tbc
- Status of CCS in Norway: From research to full-scale – Aage Stangeland, Norwegian Research Council
- EEA and Norway Grants 2014-2021 Jiří Hodík, Ministry of Finance of the Czech Republic
- The KAPPA Programme – Dominka Pačliková, Technology Agency of the Czech Republic

10:55 – 11:10 Break

11:10 – 11:50 Session 2 – CCS projects of the KAPPA programme

- CO2-SPICER – CO2 Storage Pilot In a Carbonate Reservoir – Vít Hladík, Czech Geological Survey / Vladimír Opletal, MND / Roman Berenblyum, NORCE
- METAMORPH – Advanced Hybrid Nano-fibre Membranes for CO2 Capture and Utilization – Aiva Simaite, InoCure

11:50 – 12:45 Session 3 – Other CCUS initiatives in Czechia

- Bio-CCS/U - Research centre for low-carbon energy technologies – Jan Hrdlička, Czech Technical University in Prague
- Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region – Vladimír Bartovic, EUROPEUM Institute for European Policy
- CCUS CZ-NO: The opportunity for Czech companies interested in CCUS - Gabriela Kalužová, BeePartner a. s.
- Presentations of first CCUS initiatives by Czech industrial companies – tbc

12:45 – 13:00 Final discussion

**REGISTER
HERE**

Conference language will be English.
SW platform to be used – Webex or GoToWebinar (tbc)

2.2.2 2nd Announcement

2nd Announcement

Online, 5 March 2021, 9:00-13:00

Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS

Launch event of CCS-related research and innovation projects supported from the TAČR KAPPA programme

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- Presentation by the Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic – tbc
- Status of CCS in Norway: From research to full-scale – Aage Stangeland, Norwegian Research Council
- EEA and Norway Grants 2014-2021 and the KAPPA Programme – Zuzana Dostálová, Technology Agency of the Czech Republic

10:45 – 11:00 Break

11:00 – 11:40 Session 2 – CCS projects of the KAPPA programme

- CO₂-SPICER – CO₂ Storage Pilot In a Carbonate Reservoir – Vít Hladík, Czech Geological Survey / Vladimír Opletal, MND / Roman Berenblyum, NORCE
- METAMORPH – Advanced Hybrid Nano-fibre Membranes for CO₂ Capture and Utilization – Aiva Simaite, InoCure / Miroslav Šoóš, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague

11:40 – 12:45 Session 3 – Other CCUS initiatives in Czechia

- Presentation by MND a.s. – tbc
- Bio-CCS/U - Research centre for low-carbon energy technologies – Jan Hrdlička, Czech Technical University in Prague
- Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region – Vladimír Bartovic, EUROPEUM Institute for European Policy
- CCUS CZ-NO: The opportunity for Czech companies interested in CCUS - Gabriela Kalužová, BeePartner a. s.
- Development of twin-fluid atomizer for effective CO₂ spray scrubbing subsystem and optimization of process parameters – Jan Jedelský, Brno University of Technology

12:45 – 13:00 Final discussion

Conference language will be English.

SW platform used – Webex (<https://help.webex.com/en-us/n62wi3c/Get-Started-with-Cisco-Webex-Meetings-for-Attendees>)

Organising committee:

Vít Hladík, Eva Hudečková, Vladimír Kolejka, Patrik Fiferna (Czech Geological Survey)

Aiva Simate (InoCure)

The CO2-SPICER and METAMORPH projects benefit from a grant from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

2.2.3 Final Announcement

Final Programme
Online, 5 March 2021, 9:00-13:00

Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS
Launch event of CCS-related research and innovation projects supported from the TAČR KAPPA programme

Leaders of the newly launched Czech-Norwegian research & innovation projects CO2-SPICER and METAMORPH, supported by Norway Grants and the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic within the KAPPA Programme, would like to welcome you to this online Launch event. The half-day web-conference will not only introduce the two projects in question, but also provide insight to a broader context of the CCS technology development in the framework of the accelerated economy decarbonisation efforts in the Czech Republic and Europe. The presentations will also include other CCUS projects and initiatives currently ongoing in Czechia, reflecting the increased momentum of the CCUS technology development we are now experiencing.

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- Energy policy of the Czech Republic and the role of CCS/CCU – [Tomáš Smejkal](#), Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic
- Status of CCS in Norway: From research to full-scale – [Aage Stangeland](#), Norwegian Research Council
- EEA and Norway Grants 2014-2021 and the KAPPA Programme – [Zuzana Dostálová](#), Technology Agency of the Czech Republic

10:45 – 11:00 Break

11:00 – 11:45 Session 2 – CCS projects of the KAPPA programme

- CO2-SPICER – CO2 Storage Pilot In a [CarbonatE](#) Reservoir – [Vít Hladík](#), Czech Geological Survey / [Vladimír Opletal](#), MND / [Roman Berenblyum](#), NORCE
- METAMORPH – Advanced Hybrid Nano-fibre Membranes for CO2 Capture and Utilization – [Aiva Simaite](#), InoCure / [Miroslav Šoňš](#), University of Chemistry and Technology Prague

11:45 – 12:40 Session 3 – Other CCUS initiatives in [Czechia](#)

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- CCUS CZ-NO: The opportunity for Czech companies interested in CCUS – [Gabriela Kalužová](#), [BeePartner](#) a. s.
- Development of twin-fluid atomizer for effective CO2 spray scrubbing subsystem and optimization of process parameters – [Jan Jedelský](#), Brno University of Technology

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Conference language is English.

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Organising committee:

Vít Hladík, Eva Hudečková, Vladimír Kolejka, Patrik Fiferňa (Czech Geological Survey)

Aiva Simaite (InoCure)

The CO2-SPICER and METAMORPH projects benefit from a grant from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

2.3 Participants

2.3.1 Screenshot with participants in SW platform Webex

The screenshot displays a Cisco Webex meeting interface. At the top, it shows 'Cisco Webex Meetings', 'Meeting Info', and 'Hide Menu Bar'. Below this is a menu bar with 'File', 'Edit', 'Share', 'View', 'Audio & Video', 'Participant', 'Meeting', 'Breakout Sessions', and 'Help'. The main area shows a grid of video thumbnails for participants. The current speaker is Vít Hladík (Cohost). On the right side, there is a 'Participants (70)' panel with a search bar and a list of names, each with a status icon (muted, video off, etc.). The list includes names like Jan Brothánek, Jan Hrdlička, Jan Hruby, Jan Jedelský, Jan Mrlina, Jan Theulen, Jan Tůma, Jana Malhocka, Jiří Krčmář, Jitka Jeníková, Juraj Francu, Lubomír MAZOUCH, Lukáš Pilar, Markéta Kühnelová, and Martin Hrubeš. At the bottom of the interface, there are controls for 'Unmute', 'Stop video', 'Share', and a red 'X' button.

2.4 Published news

2.4.1 Website <https://co2-spicer.geology.cz>

CO₂ SPICER
CO₂ Storage Pilot in a Carbonate Reservoir

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CZECH-NORWEGIAN CONFERENCE ON CO₂ CAPTURE AND STORAGE TOOK PLACE ONLINE

09-03-2021 12:11:28

On 5 March 2021, the Czech Geological Survey organized the conference Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS, focused on the CO₂ capture and storage technology. Due to the regulations taken by the government to overcome the coronavirus epidemic, the conference took place online. The guests were welcomed by the ambassador of the Kingdom of Norway in the Czech Republic, H. E. Robert Kvile, the Director of the Czech Geological Survey, Mr. Zdeněk Venera, and the Director of the InoCure company, Mr. Matej Buzgo. More than 70 conference participants were provided with presentations providing an idea on the role and status of CO₂ capture and storage technologies in the CR and possible ways of their implementation, as well as with insight into broader development context of these technologies in Europe.

The conference was also the launch event of the CO₂-SPICER a METAMORPH projects. These projects focus on research and development of CO₂ capture and storage technologies and are funded by the Norway Grants and the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic within the KAPPA programme. The Czech Geological Survey is the coordinator of the CO₂-SPICER project.

[Conference presentations](#)

NEWS

- CO₂-SPICER project information leaflet for download
25-03-2021 11:18:26
- Czech-Norwegian conference on CO₂ capture and storage took place online
09-03-2021 12:11:28
- Czech-Norwegian web-conference on CO₂ capture and storage
25-02-2021 11:53:37

2.4.2 Website www.geology.cz

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Czech-Norwegian conference on CO₂ capture and storage took place online

March 9, 2021

On 5 March 2021, the Czech Geological Survey organized the conference *Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS*, focused on the CO₂ capture and storage technology. Due to the regulations taken by the government to overcome the coronavirus epidemic, the conference took place online. The guests were welcomed by the ambassador of the Kingdom of Norway in the Czech Republic, H. E. Robert Kvile, the Director of the Czech Geological Survey, Mr. Zdeněk Venera, and the Director of the InoCure company, Mr. Matej Buzgo. More than 70 conference participants were provided with presentations providing an idea on the role and status of CO₂ capture and storage technologies in the CR and possible ways of their implementation, as well as with insight into broader development context of these technologies in Europe.

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Author: Klára Froňková

Attached files

[Photo from the online conference Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS](#)

CURRENT EVENTS

Geological 3D model for planning of the Střešovice railway tunnel in Prague available for interactive online viewing
April 3, 2021

CO₂-SPICER project information leaflet for download
March 25, 2021

Czech-Norwegian conference on CO₂ capture and storage took place online
March 9, 2021

Czech-Norwegian web-conference on CO₂ capture and storage
February 25, 2021

Conceptual 3D geological model of the Rožná uranium deposit available online
February 5, 2021

+ More events

CONTACTS

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 Czech Geological Survey
 Klárov 131/3
 118 21 Praha 1
 phone: +420257089448
radek.svtil@geology.cz

2.4.3 Website www.geology.cz/ccs

Informační portál

pro technologie zachytávání a ukládání CO₂

[Úvodní stránka](#) > [Novinky](#) > [Text aktuality](#)

[Úvodní stránka](#)

[Novinky](#)

[Kalendář](#)

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[Slovníček pojmů](#)

[Technologie CCS](#)

[Vliv CO₂ na změnu klimatu](#)

[Zachytávání CO₂](#)

[Přeprava CO₂](#)

[Ukládání CO₂](#)

[CCS v praxi](#)

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Česko-norská konference o zachytávání a ukládání CO₂ se uskutečnila on-line

9. března 2021

Česká geologická služba uspořádala dne 5. 3. 2021 česko-norskou konferenci *Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS* s tematikou zachytávání a ukládání CO₂. Konference se s ohledem na vládní nařízení související s bojem proti epidemii koronaviru konala on-line a úvodního přivítání hostů se ujali velvyslanec Norského království v ČR Robert Kvile, ředitel České geologické služby Zdeněk Venera a ředitel společnosti InoCure Matej Buzgo. Pro více než 70 účastníků byly připraveny prezentace přibližující technologie zachytávání a ukládání CO₂ v ČR i způsoby jejich implementace, a zároveň vzhled do širšího kontextu vývoje těchto technologií v celé Evropě.

Konference byla rovněž zahajovací událostí projektů CO₂-SPICER a METAMORPH, které jsou zaměřeny na výzkum a vývoj technologií zachytávání a ukládání CO₂ a jsou podpořeny grantem Norska a Technologické agentury České republiky prostřednictvím programu KAPPA. Česká geologická služba je hlavním řešitelem projektu CO₂-SPICER.

Autor: Klára Froňková

[Připojené soubory](#)

[Fotografie z on-line konference Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS](#)

[Přihlášení](#)

2.5 Conference presentations

CO₂ Storage Pilot in a Carbonate Reservoir

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DOWNLOADS

Documents for download.

Promotional materials

- CO₂-SPICER - Project information leaflet

Conference presentations - Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS, 5 March 2021

- Pavel Záměslický (Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic): Decarbonisation of the Czech economy
- Tomáš Smejkal (Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic): Energy policy of CZ and the role of CCS/CCU
- Aage Stangeland (Norwegian Research Council): Status of CCS in Norway: From research to full-scale
- Zuzana Dostálová (Technology Agency of the Czech Republic): EEA and Norway Grants 2014-2021 and the KAPPA Programme
- Vít Hladík (Czech Geological Survey), Vladimír Opletal (MND), Roman Berenblyum (NORCE): CO₂-SPICER – CO₂ Storage Pilot In a Carbonate Reservoir
- Aiva Simaite (InoCure), Miroslav Šoóš (University of Chemistry and Technology Prague): METAMORPH – Advanced Hybrid Nano-fibre Membranes for CO₂ Capture and Utilization
- Jan Hrdlička (Czech Technical University in Prague): Bio-CCS/U - Research centre for low-carbon energy technologies
- Vladimír Bartovic (EUROPEUM Institute for European Policy): Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region
- Gabriela Kalužová (BeePartner a. s.): CCUS CZ-NO: The opportunity for Czech companies interested in CCUS
- Jan Jedelský (Brno University of Technology): Development of twin-fluid atomizer for effective CO₂ spray scrubbing subsystem and optimization of process parameters

This report is a result of the CO₂-SPICER project
(CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir) - project No: TO01000112.

The CO₂-SPICER project benefits from a €2.32 mil grant
from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

Programme **Kappa**

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